

Soil and crop management

Effect of herbicides on azolla

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A randomized complete block design with three replications was used to determine the effect of some herbicides on azolla (*Azolla pinnata* R. Br.) in transplanted rice. Azolla at a rate of 300 g fresh weight/m² was inoculated into plots immediately after transplanting. The rates and times of herbicide application are shown in the table.

All herbicides used were deleterious to azolla and caused a significant reduction in fresh weight 30 days after transplanting (DT) (see table). Of those applied 4 DT, 2,4-D caused the least reduction in growth. Propanil was more detrimental than 2,4-D applied 21 DT.

When 2,4-D was applied 4 DT, there

Fresh weight (g/m²) of azolla 30 days after transplanting as affected by herbicide application. IRRI, 1980 wet season.

Treatment	Rate of application (kg/ha)	Time of application (DT) ^a	Azolla fresh wt ^b (g/m ²)	
Thiobencarb	1.0	4	418.0	d
Propanil	3.0	21	536.3	d
Piperophos - 2,4-D	1.5	4	667.7	cd
Butachlor	1.0	4	814.3	cd
2,4-D (liquid)	0.5	21	1420.6	bc
2,4-D (granule)	0.8	4	1660.3	b
Untreated	—	—	2840.0	a

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

was a general thickening of the azolla layer, followed by yellowing of the plants and localized death. Eventually, some recovery was observed. With other herbicides applied 4 DT, the azolla layer turned red or purple, then black. Virtually no recovery occurred.

Of the herbicides applied 21 DT, propanil was more rapid in action than 2,4-D. No recovery was observed in

either plot 9 days later.

From these results, it appears unlikely that herbicides can be used for weed control when rice is to be inoculated with azolla. The weeds will have to be controlled by other means, such as by the suppressive effect of azolla itself, by hand weeding or by using a rotary weeder at the time azolla is incorporated into the soil. ■

Azolla influence on rice yield

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The effect of azolla on paddy rice yields was studied in June-September and October-February 1980-81. A randomized block design with 10 treatments and 3 replications examined the effect of different levels of nitrogen (N) and nitrogen plus azolla. Phosphorus (P₂O₅) and potassium (K₂O) were applied uniformly at 50-50 kg/ha as basal dressing. Spacing was 20 × 10 cm.

Azolla was applied at 300 g/m² on the week after transplanting and incorporated 15 days later. Variety TKM9 was raised in the first season and IR20 in the second.

Azolla contributed to yield increase in both seasons (Table 1). In the first season, the yield with 50 kg N/ha + azolla equaled that with 75 kg N/ha. A similar trend with 25 kg N + azolla and 50 kg N/ha was seen in the second season.

Table 1. Effect of azolla on yield at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-81.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Jun-Sep		Oct-Feb	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Increase over control (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Increase over control (%)
0 N (control)	8.6	—	4.5	—
0 N + azolla	8.8	2.3	4.7	4.4
25 N	9.0	4.7	4.9	8.9
25 N + azolla	9.0	4.7	5.0	11.1
50 N	9.2	7.0	4.9	8.9
50 N + azolla	9.4	9.3	5.0	11.1
75 N	9.4	9.3	5.2	15.6
75 N + azolla	9.7	12.8	5.4	20.0
100 N	9.0	4.7	5.3	17.8
100 N + azolla	9.7	12.8	5.5	22.2
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)	ns		0.49	

Table 2. Azolla weight and multiplication ratio at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-81.

Treatment	Azolla mean weight (kg)	Multiplication ratio for 16 days
200 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	1.8	9.0
200 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	1.8	9.3
400 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	2.0	4.9
400 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	2.1	5.2
800 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	2.2	2.7
800 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	2.2	2.8
1,600 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	2.4	1.5
1,600 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	2.3	1.5

An observational trial to find the rate of azolla multiplication in February-April 1981 examined 4 levels of azolla (200, 400, 800, 1600 g/m²) and 2 levels of superphosphate (50, 100 g/m²) in 5 replications.

Multiplication of azolla was highest (9 times original level) at the low inoculation level of 200 g/m² (Table 2). There was not much difference between the two superphosphate levels. Azolla at 200

g with 50 g superphosphate/m² seems to multiply well.

The maximum temperature range was 29-39° C. It also appears that azolla multiplies well at higher temperatures. ■

Effect of neem cake-blended urea on the yield of wetland rice

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Trials at University Research Centre, Aduthurai, during 1978-79 kharif assessed the merits of neem cake-coated urea and coal-tar-treated urea basally or split applied. The soil is clay loam with low nitrogen, medium phosphorus, and high potassium. Soil pH is 7.5. The rice variety tested was IR20.

The trials were laid in a randomized block design replicated four times. Urea was mixed with neem cake by 1) blending the cake with 30% by weight of urea in a plastic bag shaken vigorously, and 2) mixing the cake with 30% by weight

Effect of neem cake-blended urea on rice yields. Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	1978	1979
Control	2.2	4.9
Urea-blended neem cake @ 30% by weight, basal application	2.8	5.0
Urea-coated neem cake (30%) using coal tar and kerosene, basal application	2.6	5.1
Urea coated with coal tar and kerosene, basal application	2.7	5.2
Incorporation of neem cake in flooded soil, followed in a week by urea, basal application	3.1	5.6
Urea only, basal application	2.9	5.3
Urea split application (25% basal, 50% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation)	3.4	5.9
Urea coated with coal tar and kerosene, split application (25% basal, 50% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation)	3.6	6.0
SE	0.22	0.10
CD	0.50	0.29

of urea pretreated with a solution of coal tar and kerosene.

Split application of coal tar- and kerosene-coated urea recorded significantly higher grain yields than all treatments except split application of urea

alone (see table).

Treating urea with coal tar and kerosene and applying in split doses (25% basal, 50% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation) showed promise in increasing N use efficiency and grain yield. ■

Environment and its influence

Effects of laser seed treatment on rice panicle characteristics

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Four lasers (Table 1) were used in treating seeds of indica rice varieties.

Treating the variety Zhen-Zhu-Ai with He-Ne laser did not advance the date of heading (Table 2), but it increased primary rachis-branches by 13.4%, secondary rachis-branches by 11.4%, filled grains by 19.8%, and percentage of filled grains by 1.0%. The same treatment on Zhai-Ye-Qing increased the secondary rachis-branches by 13.7-38.3%, 1,000-grain weight by 6.5-11.8%, and filled grains by 4-6 grains/panicle (Table 3).

Seed treatment with Ai laser did not

Table 1. Wavelength and power density of 4 lasers. Guangzhou, China.

Laser	Wavelength	Power density ^a
CO ₂ laser	10.6 μ	20 w/cm ²
He-Ne laser	6328 Å	5 mw/cm ²
Ar ⁺ laser	4880, 5145 Å	5.7 w/cm ²
N ₂ laser	3771 Å	66-88 mw/cm ²

^aw = watts, mw = milliwatts.

Table 2. Effect of laser treatment on the heading date of rice. Guangzhou, China, 1980.

Treatment	Heading date	
	Zhen-Zhu-Ai	Zhai-Ye-Qing
Control	4 Jun	6 Jun
He-Ne laser	6 Jun	6 Jun
Ar ⁺ laser	4 Jun	8 Jun
N ₂ laser	5 Jun	6 Jun
Control	9 Jun	6 Jun
CO ₂ laser	6 Jun	9 Jun

advance panicle emergence but it increased secondary rachis-branches by

12.0% for Zhen-Zhu-Ai and by 6.6% for Zhai-Ye-Qing. The treatment also increased the percentage of filled grains by 5.0-8.8% and by 11.8% for the 2 varieties. The Ar⁺ laser was more effective for 20- to 30-minute treatments with Zhen-Zhu-Ai and for 3 minutes with Zhai-Ye-Qing.

Seed treatment with N₂ laser did not advance the heading stage of either Zhen-Zhu-Ai or Zhai-Ye-Qing, nor did it affect their dry seed status or germination rate. But it increased secondary rachis-branches of Zhen-Zhu-Ai seeds by about 32.0%, the number of grains per ear by about 12.2%, and the 1,000 grain weight about 5.5%. The N₂ laser treatment of seeds had the same effects on dry and germinating seeds of Zhai-Ye-Qing, except that it decreased the grain number per panicle. Hence, the